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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the experimental determination of the amount of released gas due to cavitation using an optical evaluation method. Cavitation is induced by the mineral oil flow through a throttle valve which characterizes commonly used valves in oil hydraulic systems. Cavitation zones are influenced by the defined experimental conditions. The influence of flow velocity, downstream pressure, and valve displacement on the development of gas phase due to cavitation is evaluated. Depending on the defined experimental conditions and the throttle valve displacement, a specific amount of released gas phase is monitored in the assembled observation window. The results give an overview of the amount of gas phase in the form of the bubble size distributions, volume and mass fractions that are released from the mineral oil when cavitation occurs under the defined experimental conditions. With respect to empirically acquired data, it can be said that the volume and mass fraction evolution of released gas phase, depending on the cavitation number, can be suitably described by a power law with an appropriate order of scaling. At the same time, a change in the determined curves during the initial phase of cavitation is found. Based on measured data, it can also be said that depending on the experimental conditions, up to 1 vol. % of air is present in the assembled observation window. It is also determined that up to 8% of air is released from the dissolved state depending on the achieved experimental conditions.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Multiphase flow and cavitation in oil hydraulic systems have a very significant influence on the correct operation of hydraulic equipment.^{1–8} Air can be present in hydraulic systems in various states, but free entrained air in the form of bubbles has the potential to be the most problematic. It affects the compressibility of oil resulting in a reduced bulk modulus of oil and reduced stiffness of the hydraulic system.^{9–13} Actuators will then not be achievable a fast response and precise movements depending on the input control signals. Free entrained air also affects the heat transfer, oil film thickness, oxidation stability, noise and efficiency of the hydraulic system. Therefore, air can be considered as a contaminant which is always present in liquids. Contamination of the oil hydraulic system by free entrained air can occur due to a process which is known as cavitation.^{14,15} Cavitation occurs when the pressure drops below the liquid vapor pressure where

the process of evaporation and vapor bubble formation occurs at a given liquid temperature. Subsequently, created vapor bubbles are entrained into a higher pressure field where they condense and collapse. Thus, it is the phase change between liquid and vapor when the specific conditions are achieved in the flow field which is influenced by the presence of cavitation nuclei.^{16,17} The phase change between liquid and vapor is also accompanied by a diffusion process which is known as gaseous cavitation. Gaseous cavitation is associated with the release of air bubbles from the liquid which are initially dissolved in the liquid.¹⁴ This is caused by a drop in local static pressure below the saturation pressure of the dissolved gas. Subsequently, these released air bubbles are entrained in the direction of the flow and increase or decrease their volume depending on the operating conditions. The diffusion process of entrained air bubbles back into the dissolved state reaches longer time scales in comparison to the bubble release process.

Therefore, air bubbles are entrained with the liquid and affect the properties of the entire hydraulic system. Both mentioned types of cavitation depend on the achieved conditions in the flow field, the properties of the liquid and influence each other. It is reported that up to 10% by volume of air is dissolved in mineral oil at the atmospheric pressure and temperature of 20 °C.^{21,42} As the mineral oil temperature increases, the solubility and the amount of dissolved air increases.^{18–20} At the same time, the vapor pressure of the mineral oil is in the tens and hundreds of pascals and increases with increasing oil temperature. Thus, the mineral oil has the ability to contain a greater amount of dissolved air and has a significantly lower vapor pressure in comparison to water. Such a difference in the operating liquids will subsequently be reflected in the occurrence and development of cavitation and also in the amount of released gas phase from the dissolved state.^{22,23} At the same time, gaseous cavitation can be expected to have a dominant influence on the multiphase flow in relation to cavitation during the operation of oil hydraulic equipment.

Valves of oil hydraulic systems are characterized by very small flow areas and can operate under pressures of tens to hundreds of bars. There is a large increase in flow velocity over these small areas which is proportional to the magnitude of the pressure drop at the valve. This condition can subsequently lead to a local reduction of the static pressure to the liquid vapor pressure and the formation of nucleation sites near the walls (primary) and in the detached vortices (secondary).^{35–42} In addition, the nucleation sites in the flowing liquid can be suppressed by static pressure downstream of the valve. Conversely, the insufficient magnitude of static pressure downstream of the valve and the high flow velocity can provide ideal conditions for the occurrence and development of cavitation. These areas are typical for all valves whose low pressure ports are exposed to pressures approaching the atmospheric pressure.

The knowledge of the amount of entrained air in the hydraulic system and the consideration of air mass exchange in mathematical models represents an important role for the correct prediction of the dynamic behavior of hydraulic systems and components.^{24–26} Several measuring devices and principles have been developed over the years in order to determine the amount of gas phase in the hydraulic system.^{27–30} A very widely used method is the optical method in which the images of flow areas are acquired during the measurement process.^{31,32} For example, high-speed cameras can be used for this purpose. This method also requires the recorded area to be sufficiently illuminated and the liquid to be transparent. However, it can also be affected by the presence of mechanical particles which are entrained with bubbles. Software segmentation algorithms based on different techniques are used to analyze the acquired images with entrained bubbles.^{32–34} This image analysis can then be used to determine the bubble size distributions, and subsequently the resulting volume and mass fractions of entrained bubbles which enter the recorded area. The issue of multiphase flow and the determination of the bubble size distributions in relation to cavitation during mineral oil flow is discussed by authors Iben *et al.*³¹ The authors state that the hydrodynamic cavitation and choked flow condition at the orifice significantly affect the gas release rate from the dissolved state. Here, a higher bubble release rate is associated with an increase in the number of vapor-filled cavities and an increase in the diffusion flux when the oil is supersaturated with air in the low pressure region. They also report that bubbles are observed only under the choked flow condition. The knowledge of the

bubble size distribution can also be further applied to mathematical models of the effective bulk modulus of oil and represents a new approach to solve the dynamic behavior of a hydraulic system. The authors Geng *et al.*¹² present a model derivation of the effective bulk modulus that takes into account the bubble size distribution in oil flow simulations. The authors in this study refer to the work by Tian Van de Ven¹¹ where they report that the air dissolution rate correlates with the bubble size. Thus, the consideration of bubble size distributions contributes to a more accurate description of the effective bulk modulus of oil under dynamic pressure changes.

This article focuses on one of the ways in which free entrained bubbles can naturally contaminate an oil hydraulic system and thus affecting the effective bulk modulus of oil. The effect of flow velocity, downstream pressure and the different flow field due to the change in valve displacement is evaluated. The paper provides experimentally obtained data which characterize the gas phase development due to cavitation on the complex geometry. For this purpose, the results are presented in the form of bubble size distributions, parameters of log-normal distributions, volume and mass fractions of released gas bubbles. The present experimental study aims to clarify the following points:

- Is the gas release process connected only to the choked flow condition?
- The physical processes of gaseous and vapor cavitation are known. However, is it possible to estimate which physical process is involved in the release of bubbles from the dissolved state based on the determined dependencies?
- How does the bubble size distribution change with different stages of cavitation development?

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD AND APPARATUS

The device for the experimental analysis of mineral oil flow through the investigated throttle valve, on which cavitation is induced, is proposed. The occurrence and development of cavitation is influenced by effects of increasing flow velocity, increasing downstream pressure of the valve and valve displacement during this experimental analysis. Other effects affecting the occurrence and development of cavitation are considered as constant variables. The increasing flow velocity in the narrow gap of the throttle valve amplifies cavitation and the increasing downstream pressure of the valve suppresses cavitation. The measurements are performed for 2 throttle valve openings TV2. Subsequently, these displacements affect the region which is exposed to a higher flow velocity when the mineral oil passes through the narrowest flow area of the valve under the defined experimental conditions. Depending on the achieved experimental conditions and the size of cavitation zone, the specific number of bubbles is released from the dissolved state and entrained downstream of the assembled device. The observation window OW is implemented behind the throttle valve TV2 and its flow area is recorded by the high-speed camera HSC. In this way, it is possible to record a specific flow area and determine the concentration of released bubbles in relation to the different stages of cavitation development. The distance between the recorded area of the observation window OW and the cavitation zone is approximately 230 mm. The mineral oil is heated to the required oil temperature before the measurements are started. Simultaneously with this procedure, the recirculation of the mineral oil through the assembled

experimental device is realized to achieve a homogeneous dispersion of the cavitation nuclei. Figure 1 shows the simplified hydraulic circuit of the experimental device for the analysis of the flow through the investigated throttle valve TV2 and the determination of bubble size distributions in the observation window OW.

The mineral oil is delivered through the high pressure pipeline P to the assembled experimental device. The throttle valve TV1 provides the flow dividing function. This configuration provides finer adjustment of the required oil volume flow rate passing through the throttle valve TV2. The experiment is performed for 2 valve displacements TV2, specifically $s_1 = 1.31$ mm and $s_2 = 2.31$ mm. The throttle valve TV3 is implemented behind the observation window OW to ensure the constant pressure conditions downstream of the valve $p_{3,rel.} = 0.5 \cdot 10^5$; $1.0 \cdot 10^5$; and $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ Pa when the oil volume flow rate changes. The oil volume flow rate is measured by the flow meter SFR which is implemented upstream of the valve TV2. The mineral oil is returned to the tank of hydraulic unit using the low pressure pipeline T. The experiment is terminated when the upstream pressure of the throttle valve TV2 reaches $p_{1,rel.} = 40 \cdot 10^5$ Pa due to the strength of the transparent block. The bubble size distributions, including volume and mass fractions, are evaluated in the initial phase of cavitation occurrence. The constant mineral oil temperature is ensured by the secondary unit for the liquid

temperature adjustment which includes an air cooler and a pair of heating elements. The constant oil temperature is ensured during the experiment using two-position control with the defined hysteresis of $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The oil temperature is measured by the temperature sensor ST upstream of the valve TV2. During the experiment, the oil temperature is in the range of $t_o = (39.5 \text{ to } 41.6)^\circ\text{C}$. The hydraulic unit also contains low and high pressure filters to ensure the filtration of mechanical particles larger than $6 \mu\text{m}$. It can be assumed that mechanical particles do not affect the results of determined bubble size distributions. This is due to the very small size of mechanical particles in comparison to the 1 pixel size of the acquired image, see Sec. II B 2. The mineral oil HV46 is used to perform the experimental measurements. The dependencies of density and dynamic viscosity on the temperature are experimentally determined for this oil. The physical properties, which are considered in the evaluation of the experiment, are summarized in Table 1 for the oil temperature $t_o \approx 40^\circ\text{C}$.

The static characteristics of the throttle valve TV2 are measured on the assembled device and operating points, which correspond to the cavitation inception, are marked. The hydraulic quantities are recorded with the recording time of 5 s and the sampling frequency of 10 ms. Subsequently, the individual operating points of the determined static characteristics are evaluated from these recordings.

FIG. 1. Device for experimental study of multiphase flow caused by cavitation.

TABLE I. Physical properties of mineral oil HV46.

Oil dynamic viscosity $\eta_O / \text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$	0.03859
Oil kinematic viscosity $\nu_O / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	45.3
Oil density $\rho_O / \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$	852
Oil vapor pressure $p_{v,O} / \text{Pa}$	≈ 20

A. Visualization of flow through throttle valve

The throttle valve TV2 is implemented in the transparent block which provides the visualization of flow at the various experimental conditions. During each measurement, the images of the throttle valve flow area are acquired using the camera C with lens L2, see Fig. 1. The camera C is used to acquire images with the relatively long exposure time of $t = 1/2000 \text{ s}$ and the background behind the throttle valve TV2 is backlighted to reach greater contrast with the cavitation zone. The position of the valve throttle edge TV2 in the transparent block is adjusted so that the cavitation zone is affected as little as possible by swirling for the purpose of experimental measurements. Thus, the flow is directed into the vertical channel immediately when the oil passes through the narrowest flow area S_{NCS} . The throttle edge position in relation to the seat can be seen in Fig. 2. This position allows the best images of the inception and the development of cavitation zone to be acquired from the experimental point of view.

The valve displacements in relation to the seat of the transparent block are determined based on the reference distance between two pixels of the known object (i.e., throttle valve diameter $\phi d = 8 \text{ mm}$) and the resolution of acquired images. The Photron Fastcam Viewer software is used for these purposes allowing the number of pixels per millimeter of length to be determined and the resulting displacements to be evaluated. The valve displacements in relation to the block seat correspond to $s_1 = 1.31 \text{ mm}$ and $s_2 = 2.31 \text{ mm}$. These valve displacements are selected to achieve a sufficient number of operating points at which cavitation is developed. At the same time, the valve displacements are not affected by the large opening at which the valve is almost out of the block seat. The noncircular flow areas S_{NCS} are determined based on the known geometry of the transparent block, the geometry and displacements of the throttle valve TV2. In the case of the displacement of $s_1 = 1.31 \text{ mm}$, the narrowest flow area of the valve corresponds to $S_{NCS} = 0.51 \text{ mm}^2$. In the case of the displacement of $s_2 = 2.31 \text{ mm}$, the narrowest flow area of the valve corresponds to $S_{NCS} = 1.19 \text{ mm}^2$. The displacement analysis and the determination of the narrowest flow areas of the throttle valve TV2 are necessary for the further evaluation of the experiment.

FIG. 2. Throttle valve displacements, (a) $s_1 = 1.31 \text{ mm}$ and (b) $s_2 = 2.31 \text{ mm}$.

B. Optical measurement method

The design is proposed to determine the amount of released gas due to cavitation in the throttle valve. The design for monitoring the released gas phase consists of the observation window OW which is made of a transparent material. The flow area of the observation window OW in the recording area of the high-speed camera is proposed as rectangular. The change from the circular flow area to the rectangular flow area is proposed to avoid issues with the circular wall curvature and a distorted view of bubble sizes. This rectangular flow area also provides the capability to partially minimize the issue of individual bubble overlap at high concentrations. Thus, released bubbles are distributed over the width of the observation window OW. Also, the rectangular flow area is proposed to ensure a nearly constant flow velocity. In this way, it is possible to avoid issues with the bubble size change due to the changes of flow velocity and pressure. The assembled observation window OW for monitoring entrained bubbles is implemented behind the throttle valve TV2, see Fig. 1. Figure 3 shows the proposed design for monitoring the bubble size distributions and the marked flow area which is recorded using the high-speed camera HSC with the lens L1. This assembly also includes the set of three extension tubes ET which allow the optical elements to be moved further away from the camera sensor. This subsequently provides a shorter focus distance and better resolution of recorded bubbles.

FIG. 3. (a) Observation window (dimensions in millimeter) and (b) Field of focus, $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}$ scale grid.

The analysis is performed considering the achieved flow regime in the assembled observation window OW. The Reynolds number and the mean flow velocity are determined for the maximum volume flow rate $Q_{v,O,max}$, which is achieved during the experiment for the individual valve displacements. The values of Reynolds numbers Re_C , Re_R , and the mean flow velocities v_C , v_R are presented in Table II. The subscript C is used for the circular flow area and the subscript R for the rectangular flow area.

It can be said from the results presented in Table II that depending on the relatively small volume flow rate, the mineral oil HV46, and the geometrical parameters of the observation window OW, the laminar flow regime is achieved over the entire experiment.

A specific volume of the observation window OW, which is marked by the letter F in Fig. 3, is considered for the determination of released bubble concentrations. The marked area F represents the volume V_S in which recorded bubbles may appear sharp in relation to the recording setup and the applied recording equipment. Out of the marked area, recorded bubbles do not reach a sufficient contrast for the segmentation purposes. It is necessary to determine the depth of field to correctly determine the number of released bubbles within the recorded volume V_S .

1. Depth of field measurements

To properly determine the recorded area, the test measurements are performed to evaluate the depth of field with respect to the different aperture settings of the lens L1. The configuration of the depth of field test measurements corresponds to the same setting at which the bubble size distribution measurements are performed. For the bubble size distribution measurements, the aperture of the lens L1 is set to the higher aperture number of $f/16$ to achieve a deeper depth of field. The depth of field is also affected by the distance between the high-speed camera HSC and the focus plane. This distance corresponds to ≈ 0.95 m and correlates with the bubble size distribution measurements. The simple device with the 45° inclined plane, on which the millimeter scale is implemented, is assembled to perform the depth of field test measurements, see Fig. 4. The output of the measurements are images of the millimeter scale that are acquired using the high-speed camera HSC with the resolution of 1280×1024 pixels.

The focus plane is set to the zeroth division of the millimeter scale. The images of the scale are acquired for the selected lens aperture setting. The pixel brightness levels are evaluated for the quantitative evaluation of the depth of field. The pixel brightness levels are evaluated for an identically defined column of pixels. Figure 5 shows and compares the evaluated pixel brightness levels for the selected aperture settings of $f/5.6$ and $f/16$. Figure 5 also shows the background brightness levels of the images, which can be considered as a reference, and the minimum brightness levels. The brightest level corresponds to 255

TABLE II. Evaluation of flow regime in observation window.

	$Q_{v,O,max}$ ($dm^3 \cdot min^{-1}$)	v_C ($m \cdot s^{-1}$)	v_R ($m \cdot s^{-1}$)	Re_C (-)	Re_R (-)
$s_1 = 1.31$ mm	2.50	0.133	0.124	59	30
$s_2 = 2.31$ mm	5.75	0.305	0.285	135	68

FIG. 4. Device for depth of field test measurements.

and the darkest possible level corresponds to 0 with respect to the 8-bit image. The depth of field is evaluated according to the range where the minimum brightness level is achieved. Thus, the darkest brightness levels and a relatively sharp transition between the defined brightness levels can be observed nearby the focus plane.

The acquired images for the determination of depth of field at the different aperture numbers are shown in Fig. 6. The evaluated brightness levels are also included in Fig. 6. It is necessary to take into account the distortion of the view due to the inclined plane when the depth of field is determined. The scale division, corresponding to 1 mm, is also indicated in Fig. 6 for illustrative purposes. The projection of this scale division onto the horizontal plane XZ, see Fig. 4, gives the depth of field (DOF) value of 0.707 mm. For the sake of illustration, the thickness of the millimeter scale line after projection onto the vertical plane YZ, see Fig. 4, corresponds to ≈ 100 μ m.

It can be said that the depth of field increases with increasing aperture number depending on the acquired images from the test measurements. However, as the aperture number increases, less light is transmitted to the camera sensor and the dynamic range of the acquired image is reduced. For this reason, the exposure time has to be adjusted. The aperture numbers of $f/16$ and $f/22$ offer a relatively large depth of field achieving visible bubbles over the entire depth of the recorded area of the observation window OW (i.e., 6 mm). Anyway, the image sharpness is reduced with higher aperture numbers due to the light diffraction. In addition, the sharpness and brightness level of recorded bubbles may be affected by the size of bubbles whose mean diameter is approximately 45 μ m, see Sec. III C. Figure 6 also shows a selected image of bubbles which is recorded during the bubble size distribution measurements under the defined experimental conditions. It is possible to observe the decrease in sharpness and the increase in brightness level of recorded bubbles that are located at a larger distance from the focus plane. After the visual and quantitative evaluation of acquired images, it can be said that sufficiently sharp bubbles can be

FIG. 5. Brightness level evaluation.

FIG. 6. Images for depth of field (DOF) evaluation (a) $f/5.6$, (b) $f/8$, (c) $f/11$, (d) $f/16$, (e) $f/22$, and (f) Experimental condition: $s(\text{mm}) / Q_v (\text{dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}) / \Delta p (\text{Pa}) / p_{3,\text{rel.}} (\text{Pa}) / \sigma_{v2}$ (-): $1.31 / 1.60 / 18.9 \cdot 10^5 / 0.5 \cdot 10^5 / 0.133, 1 \times 1 \text{ mm}$ scale grid.

observed in the depth of 2.8 mm when the aperture number is $f/16$ and the focus distance is $\approx 0.95 \text{ m}$.

2. Bubble size distribution measurements

The recorded area F , in which sharp bubbles are detected, has dimensions of $14.65 \times 11.72 \times 2.8 \text{ mm}$ and represents the volume of $V_S = 481 \text{ mm}^3$. The entire recorded depth of the flow area, which contains both in-focus and out-of-focus bubbles, has dimensions of

$14.65 \times 11.72 \times 6.0 \text{ mm}$ and represents the volume of $V_T = 1030 \text{ mm}^3$. The above-mentioned sizes of defined areas are determined based on the image calibration. In essence, this is the determination of the number of pixels per millimeter of length for the recorded area. This step is performed using the resolution of the images and the known dimension of the object in the analyzed image. The ground, thin prism with defined dimensions, on which the focus is performed, is placed on the front and back wall of the observation window OW before the measurements are started. The width of the ground prism is determined

with a micrometer and corresponds to the size of 8.96 mm. The calibration values, corresponding to the walls of the observation window OW, are 90.1 and 84.8 pix./mm. For the sake of simplification, a linear change in the number of pixels per millimeter of length is considered when the focus plane is changed. Subsequently, the calibration value in the area of mineral oil with bubbles corresponds to 87.3 pix./mm. The acquired images of the ground prism for calibration purposes are shown in Fig. 7. The determined calibration value is also used as the input parameter of the software to solve the segmentation of bubbles in the image.

The flow velocity in the observation window OW increases with increasing oil volume flow rate during the experiment. This increase in flow velocity then affects the required exposure time at which recording is performed. The relatively short exposure time is set to $t = 1/20\,000$ s to ensure a sufficiently sharp image during a higher flow velocity. When the longer exposure time is chosen, the motion blur occurs which would subsequently affect the bubble size during segmentation. As the exposure time decreases, less light is transmitted to the camera sensor and the dynamic range of the acquired image is affected again. However, the sharpness of the image with increasing flow velocity is achieved.

The high-speed camera provides the frame rate of 2000 fps at the default image resolution of 1280×1024 pixels. To avoid recounting of already determined bubble size distributions within a short recording interval and to achieve an average bubble representation within a longer recording interval, the frame rate is reduced to 50 fps when the default image resolution is preserved. In this way, the recording is obtained that corresponds to time of $t \approx 83$ s. In addition, 22 frames (~ 1 frame every 4 s) are selected from the total number of frames of the recording which are then evaluated by an image analysis software. This software is based on a segmentation algorithm which contains a sequence of actions for the resulting image analysis. The algorithm, which is used to analyze the acquired images, is a part of the open-source software Bubble Analyzer.³⁴ The Bubble Analyzer software also allows a user to include an image where no bubbles are present. This image is then used to correct the background during bubble segmentation and helps the algorithm to process the image. The image is acquired before the measurements are started. The output of the image analysis using Bubble Analyzer software is a dataset of all segmented

bubbles that are analyzed by the segmentation algorithm within 1 recording. To determine the histogram of bubbles corresponding to 1 frame, the resulting histogram is divided by the number of used frames. In essence, this is the time-averaged bubble size distribution corresponding to 1 operating point during the time interval $t \approx 83$ s. At the same time, the histograms of recorded bubbles are determined for 1 cm^3 in relation to the known recorded area of the observation window V_S . Three recordings are performed in sequence to obtain 1 operating point of measurements. The bubble size distributions, the volume and mass fractions of gas phase are determined for each recording. The output of the given operating point is the average of these quantities from 3 repeated measurements. The total number of 3×22 images are evaluated to obtain 1 operating point which are acquired at the time interval $t \approx 3 \times 83$ s. The resulting bubble size distributions, including the determined dependencies of the volume and mass fractions, are supplemented with deviations.

The results of the time-averaged bubble size distributions using Bubble Analyzer software are then compared with some manually determined bubble counts. Six images with a relatively low bubble concentration, which are acquired under the different experimental conditions, are selected for these purposes. For the sake of illustration, Fig. 8 shows the manually evaluated bubble counts on 2 selected images that are acquired under the same experimental conditions. The experimental conditions can be seen in Fig. 8. The manually evaluated bubbles are marked red and blue in the images.

Both in-focus and out-of-focus bubbles, which are present in the selected images, are counted into the total number of bubbles. With respect to the depth of field test measurements at the aperture number $f/16$, it can be said that the manually evaluated bubbles can be identified in the entire recorded depth of the flow area of observation window, i.e., 6 mm ($V_T = 1030\text{ mm}^3$). Therefore, the manually evaluated bubble counts (total number of bubbles 920 ± 99) can be approximately compared with the evaluated histograms of bubbles that are determined using the image analysis software (total number of bubbles 845 ± 50). It can be said from the comparison that the results approach each other. Although the relatively larger volume $V_T = 1030\text{ mm}^3$ is manifested in the mutual comparison. The same conclusion can be said for the other selected images which are acquired under the different experimental conditions.

FIG. 7. Image calibration, 1×1 mm scale grid, (a) the front wall of OW and (b) the back wall of OW.

FIG. 8. Manually evaluated bubble counts.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Static characteristics

The cavitation number σ_v is introduced for the quantitative evaluation of cavitation. This number describes how close the pressure in the flow field is to the liquid vapor pressure and represents the stage of cavitation development. The dimensionless cavitation number σ_v can be defined based on equations which take into account the achieved hydrodynamic parameters in the liquid:

$$\sigma_v = \frac{2(p_{ref.} - p_v)}{\rho_l v_l^2}, \quad (1)$$

eventually:

$$\sigma_v = \frac{p_{ref.} - p_v}{\Delta p}, \quad (2)$$

where $p_{ref.}$ is the absolute pressure in a specific location of flow field, p_v is the liquid vapor pressure, ρ_l is the liquid density, v_l is a specific flow velocity of the liquid, $\Delta p = p_1 - p_2$ is the pressure drop. The second formulation of the cavitation number is often used in the investigation of closed channel flows, for example, through valves, where the pressure drop Δp is directly related to the velocity of the liquid jet after passing through the flow area of the valve. The dynamic pressure is affected by the liquid density and the mean flow velocity v_{NCS} in the first formulation which can be determined based on the known narrowest flow area of the valve S_{NCS} and the measured oil volume flow rate $Q_{v,O}$ according to the simplified continuity equation:

$$v_{NCS} = \frac{Q_{v,O}}{S_{NCS}}. \quad (3)$$

The cavitation occurrence and development is predominantly affected by the flow velocity through the narrowest flow area of the valve S_{NCS} and also by the downstream pressure of the valve $p_{2,abs.}$ which surrounds cavitation zones. Therefore, the formula for calculation of the cavitation number σ_{v2} is used to evaluate the cavitation zones which takes into account these two parameters:

$$\sigma_{v2} = \frac{2(p_{2,abs.} - p_{v,O})}{\rho_O v_{NCS}^2}, \quad (4)$$

where $p_{2,abs.}$ is the absolute pressure downstream of the valve and follows $p_{2,abs.} \approx p_{3,abs.}$, $p_{v,O}$ is the oil vapor pressure, ρ_O is the oil density, v_{NCS} is the mean flow velocity in the narrowest flow area of the valve S_{NCS} . In the case of higher downstream pressure of the valve, cavitation may not occur and the cavitation number σ_{v2} will be high. Therefore, the conditions, which suppress the cavitation occurrence and development, will be dominant.

Figure 9 shows the evaluated static characteristics $\Delta p = f(Q_{v,O})$ for the valve displacements of $s_1 = 1.31 \text{ mm}$ and $s_2 = 2.31 \text{ mm}$. The mineral oil temperature is in the range of $t_O = (39.5 \text{ to } 41.6)^\circ \text{C}$ during the experiment. This effect is subsequently manifested in small deviations between the determined dependencies due to the oil dynamic viscosity change η_O . However, it can be said that this factor has a negligible effect on the resulting dependencies. Figures 9–11 shows the operating points at which cavitation occurs and entrained bubbles are detected for the first time in the observation window OW. These operating points are interpreted to be the inception of multiphase flow in relation to cavitation. The operating points are indicated by the cavitation numbers $\sigma_{v2,i}$ and distinguished by the hatched symbols according to the specified experimental conditions.

Figure 9 does not show that cavitation occurrence significantly affects the resulting static characteristics $\Delta p = f(Q_{v,O})$ of the throttle valve for both displacements and the specified experimental conditions. This may be due to the very small cavitation zone which does not significantly affect the flow through the throttle valve and does not cause a choked flow condition. For the valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31 \text{ mm}$ and the downstream pressure of $p_{3,rel.} = 0.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ Pa}$, the full range of measured volume flow rates is not achieved because the specified experimental conditions are not maintained. This is caused by the pressure loss of the pipeline T where the required downstream pressure of the valve is exceeded at a higher oil volume flow rate and the fully opened throttle valve TV3. For this reason, the measurement for this variant is terminated earlier. With respect to the illustrated operating points of cavitation inception, it can be said that in the case

FIG. 9. Dependencies of pressure drop Δp on oil volume flow rate $Q_{v,O}$.

FIG. 10. Dependencies of mean flow velocity v_{NCS} on oil volume flow rate $Q_{v,O}$.

of larger valve opening of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, the cavitation inception is less dependent on the achieved hydrodynamic parameters. In the case of smaller valve opening of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm, there is a slight offset due to the different pressure conditions at the outlet. This condition may be caused by a larger nucleation site where the conditions for the occurrence and development of cavitation are achieved. The larger nucleation site, which is exposed to a higher flow velocity, subsequently results in a lower sensitivity to the achieved hydrodynamic parameters leading to the cavitation inception.

Figure 10 shows the evaluated mean flow velocities v_{NCS} corresponding to the narrowest flow area of the valve S_{NCS} . The illustrated static characteristics $v_{NCS} = f(Q_{v,O})$ represent the linear dependence of the mean flow velocity on the oil volume flow rate. In the case of valve displacement of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm, it can be observed that a higher flow

velocity is required in the narrow gap with increasing downstream pressure to reach the cavitation inception. A more sensitive response to the achieved hydrodynamic parameters, leading to the cavitation inception, can be observed for this displacement.

Figure 11 shows the evaluated dependencies of the cavitation number on the Reynolds number. The Reynolds number is determined for the narrowest flow area of the valve S_{NCS} :

$$Re_{NCS} = 4 \frac{S_{NCS} v_{NCS} \rho_O}{o_{NCS} \eta_O}, \quad (5)$$

where η_O and ρ_O is the oil dynamic viscosity and density at a specified temperature, v_{NCS} is the mean flow velocity in the noncircular flow area, S_{NCS} is the noncircular flow area and o_{NCS} is the wetted perimeter of the noncircular flow area. It can be said from the evaluated static characteristics $\sigma_{v2} = f(Re_{NCS})$ that the cavitation number approaches zero as the Reynolds number increases. This dependence is derived from the definition of the cavitation number when the constant pressure conditions downstream of the valve are maintained and the mean flow velocity v_{NC} is increased. It can be generally said that a higher cavitation number leads to suppression of cavitation occurrence and development. As the cavitation number decreases, the cavitation zone and the amount of released gas phase increases, see Sec. III C. It can also be said from the mutual comparison that in the case of valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, cavitation occurs at a higher cavitation number indicating that cavitation develops more easily at larger valve opening. The reason for this may be the already mentioned larger nucleation site in which the conditions for cavitation occurrence are achieved.

B. Visual evaluation of cavitation zone in valve

Figure 12 shows the selected images of valve which are acquired during the experimental measurements for the valve displacement of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm. Figure 13 shows selected images of the valve for the valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm. The selected images correspond to nearly identical cavitation numbers σ_{v2} and characterize comparable conditions affecting the cavitation zones. The images are acquired with the relatively long exposure time of $t = 1/2000$ s and the aperture number of $f/2.8$. It is necessary to emphasize that such a recording equipment setup offers time-averaged documentation of the cavitation zone due to the relatively long exposure time. As the mineral oil passes through the throttle edge of the valve, there is an increase in flow

FIG. 11. Dependencies of cavitation number σ_{v2} on Reynolds number Re_{NCS} .

FIG. 12. Visual evaluation of valve displacement $s_1 = 1.31$ mm, Experimental conditions Q_v ($\text{dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) / Δp (Pa) / $p_{3,\text{rel.}}$ (Pa) / σ_{v2} (-): (a) 1.40 / $15.1 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.174, (b) 1.60 / $18.6 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.175, (c) 1.80 / $22.3 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.174, (d) 1.60 / $18.9 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.133, (e) 1.90 / $24.6 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.126, (f) 2.10 / $28.7 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.128, (g) 1.90 / $25.2 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.094, (h) 2.20 / $31.3 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.093, and (i) 2.50 / $37.8 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.090.

FIG. 13. Visual evaluation of valve displacement $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, Experimental conditions Q_v ($\text{dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) / Δp (Pa) / $p_{3,\text{rel.}}$ (Pa) / σ_{v2} (-): (j) 2.75 / $11.1 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.240, (k) 3.25 / $14.7 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.229, (l) 3.50 / $16.7 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.248, (m) 3.25 / $14.9 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.172, (n) 3.75 / $18.8 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.174, (o) 4.25 / $23.4 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.168, (p) 3.75 / $19.1 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.130, (q) 4.25 / $23.6 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.134, and (r) 4.75 / $28.4 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.133.

velocity and a local decrease in static pressure. This correlation between the flow velocity and the static pressure can be described by Bernoulli's equation which states that the total energy at any point of the flow field is constant. Thus, there is the greatest increase in flow velocity and at the same time the greatest decrease in static pressure at the point of the most restricted flow area. Cavitation can be expected to occur in these locations.

However, it is found from the performed visualization that the visible cavitation inception and the intense release of gas phase occurs at the point where the jet is detached from the throttle valve body, see Figs. 12(a)–12(c) and 13(j)–13(l). The location of the more intense gas phase release may be caused by the angle of liquid jet detachment from the throttle valve body. Depending on the angle of liquid jet detachment, a larger region is exposed to the local static pressure decrease and the liquid tensile load where the cohesive forces of liquid molecules are exceeded. Thus, the liquid integrity on the interface with the wall is disturbed over the larger area and the bubble release is more noticeable. The cavitation cloud may be affected by the detached vortices with the further increase in flow velocity which are recorded within the relatively long exposure time. These detached vortices subsequently provide another potential source of multiphase flow in relation to cavitation. It can also be observed in Figs. 12 and 13 that with respect to nearly identical cavitation numbers, the cavitation zones achieve approximately the same size for the specified displacements. Thus, the amount of released gas phase can be expected to be comparable to each other. However, this conclusion is not confirmed for the acquired images of the observation window OW where analyzed bubbles occur, see Figs. 14 and 15.

FIG. 14. Released air bubbles in observation window - valve displacement $s_1 = 1.31$ mm, Experimental conditions Q_v ($\text{dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) / Δp (Pa) / $p_{3,\text{rel.}}$ (Pa) / σ_{v2} (-): (a) 1.40 / $15.1 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.174, (b) 1.60 / $18.6 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.175, (c) 1.80 / $22.3 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.174, (d) 1.60 / $18.9 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.133, (e) 1.90 / $24.6 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.126, (f) 2.10 / $28.7 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.128, (g) 1.90 / $25.2 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.094, (h) 2.20 / $31.3 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.093, and (i) 2.50 / $37.8 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.090.

FIG. 15. Released air bubbles in observation window - valve displacement $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, Experimental conditions Q_v ($\text{dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) / Δp (Pa) / $p_{3,\text{rel.}}$ (Pa) / σ_{v2} (-): (j) 2.75 / $11.1 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.240, (k) 3.25 / $14.7 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.229, (l) 3.50 / $16.7 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.248, (m) 3.25 / $14.9 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.172, (n) 3.75 / $18.8 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.174, (o) 4.25 / $23.4 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.168, (p) 3.75 / $19.1 \cdot 10^5$ / $0.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.130, (q) 4.25 / $23.6 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.134, and (r) 4.75 / $28.4 \cdot 10^5$ / $1.5 \cdot 10^5$ / 0.133.

C. Bubble size distributions

The selected images of the observation window OW with analyzed bubbles at the displacement of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm can be observed in Fig. 14. In Fig. 15, the selected images with analyzed bubbles at the displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm can be observed. The selected images also correspond to the measurements with nearly identical cavitation numbers and characterize comparable conditions affecting the cavitation zones. The recordings of regions with entrained bubbles are not performed over the entire range of measured operating points but only for the first 10 points from the cavitation inception in the valve. The bubble concentration, which can be evaluated in the acquired images, varies significantly depending on the achieved experimental conditions. Although these images also correspond to the experimental conditions with nearly identical cavitation numbers σ_{v2} . Similar results are achieved in the case of valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, see Fig. 15.

The observed reduction of released gas phase may be caused by the effect of suppressed nucleation sites on the walls and detached vortices as the downstream pressure increases. However, the flow velocity through the valve is increased to maintain the same cavitation number with increasing downstream pressure of the valve. This may be further manifested in the increased frequency of vortex shedding. It is necessary to further analyze this issue in the field of numerical simulations using more advanced approaches to model turbulent flow through the valve due to the complexity of possible aspects affecting the development of released gas phase caused by cavitation. Subsequently, achieved results of numerical simulations will be verified by an experiment where the influence of detached vortices on the cavitation zone will be investigated using the high-speed camera.

Figures 16–18 show the resulting bubble size distributions corresponding to the valve displacements of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm and $s_2 = 2.31$ mm

FIG. 16. Time-averaged bubble size distributions for constant $p_{3,rel.} = 0.5 \cdot 10^5$ Pa – $s_1 = 1.31$ mm (I.), $s_2 = 2.31$ mm (II.).

for the different experimental conditions. The bubble size distributions are determined for the volume of 1 cm^3 and the width of each bins corresponds to $20 \mu\text{m}$. For the sake of illustration, the points (a–i) corresponding to the images in Figs. 12 and 14 are indicated for the displacement of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm. Also, the points (j–r) corresponding to the images in Figs. 13 and 15 for the displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm are indicated.

The dominant part of evaluated histograms can be observed in Figs. 16–18 which corresponds to the mean values of bubble diameters of $d_B = 32$ and $52 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting bubble size distributions may be significantly affected by turbulence which results in the bubble fragmentation into smaller sizes. Additionally, the lack of resolution of small bubbles may be manifested in the resulting histograms which may be affected by the used recording equipment, specifically the lens L1 with its relatively low magnification ratio (i.e., 1:2). Despite the fact that the set of extension tubes ET is used to achieve better details of bubbles. The number of individual analyzed bubble sizes decreases with increasing bubble size. Thus, these are asymmetric distributions with a skewness to the right which are approximated by a lognormal distribution $\ln(d_B) \sim N(\mu; \theta^2)$. The cavitation zone is more suppressed with increasing downstream pressure of the valve and there is a reduction in the number of bubbles in each bin, see Figs. 17 and 18. The bubble size distributions can be further affected by the essence of the used optical method where a 2D image is used to characterize 3D flow. Thus, there is overlap of individual bubbles in the recorded area at higher bubble concentrations which affects the resulting bubble size distributions. This condition can subsequently lead to the incorrect bubble segmentation and the distorted evaluation of the resulting

histograms where the segmentation algorithm is not able to distinguish the boundary of small bubbles and merges them into large bubbles. This negative effect increases with increasing oil volume flow rate through the throttle valve and mainly affects the results with the low downstream pressure $p_{3,rel.}$. This negative effect is more noticeable for the valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm. The significant and also improbable change in the trend of bubble distributions can be observed in comparison to the valve displacement of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm where the underestimation of small bubbles and the overestimation of large bubbles occurs. For this reason, the last 3 measured operating points for the valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm and the downstream pressure of $p_{3,rel.} = 0.5 \cdot 10^5$ Pa are considered to be rather approximate. The following Figs. 17 and 18 show the resulting bubble histograms for the other experimental conditions and the valve displacements. The bubble histograms depend on the hydrodynamic parameters of mineral oil flow through the valve which are uniformly characterized by the cavitation number, see Eq. (4).

As above-mentioned, the bubble size distributions are approximated by the lognormal distributions for which a probability density function (PDF) can be expressed:

$$P(d_B) = \frac{1}{d_B \theta \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[\frac{-(\ln d_B - \mu)^2}{2\theta^2} \right], \quad (6)$$

where d_B is the bubble diameter, μ is the mean of the natural logarithm $\ln(d_B)$ (representing the location parameter of the lognormal distribution), and θ is the standard deviation of the natural logarithm $\ln(d_B)$ (representing the scale parameter of the lognormal distribution). The

FIG. 17. Time-averaged bubble size distributions for constant $p_{3,rel.} = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$ Pa – $s_1 = 1.31$ mm (I.), $s_2 = 2.31$ mm (II.).

FIG. 18. Time-averaged bubble size distributions for constant $p_{3,rel.} = 1.5 \cdot 10^5$ Pa – $s_1 = 1.31$ mm (I.), $s_2 = 2.31$ mm (II.).

above-mentioned effects are also manifested in the determination of the probability density function and the statistical evaluation. The probability density functions for the downstream pressure of $p_{3,rel.} = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$ Pa are shown in Fig. 19 for illustrative purposes which are evaluated as the average of 3 repeated measurements.

Figure 20 shows the evaluated parameters affecting the lognormal distribution due to cavitation in the throttle valve for the full range of experimental conditions and repeated measurements.

It can be essentially said that the parameters of lognormal distribution increase with decreasing cavitation number (i.e., increasing cavitation intensity). Although it is possible to find some different curves in the determined trends depending on the experimental conditions and the valve displacements. Especially in the case of the location parameter of the lognormal distribution μ . In the case of larger valve opening of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, a stagnant trend can be observed in the initial phase of cavitation occurrence where the probability density function does not change significantly and only the number of bubbles increases. However, there is an increase from the certain operating point ($\sigma_{v2} \approx 0.20$ – 0.25). A similar result is also achieved for the smaller valve opening of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm and the downstream pressure $p_{3,rel.} = 1.5 \cdot 10^5$ Pa. However, there is a step increase in the location parameter μ at the certain operating point. No stagnant phase can be observed for the other experimental conditions and the valve displacement of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm, but the continuous increase is found. Moreover, a different rate of the location parameter increase μ can be observed. There is a noticeable deceleration in the location parameter

FIG. 19. Probability density function for constant $p_{3,rel.} = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$ Pa - $s_1 = 1.31$ mm (I.), $s_2 = 2.31$ mm (II.).

FIG. 20. Dependencies of lognormal distribution parameters on cavitation number.

growth from the certain operating point ($\sigma_{v2} \approx 0.13$ – 0.15). Effects caused by turbulent flow may be involved in the determined curves. Also, the potential effect of phase change as a result of reached vapor pressure in the flow field, which accelerates with increasing flow velocity, cannot be neglected. Figure 21 shows the evaluated statistical metrics that represent the mean, median and mode of the lognormal distribution. The resulting dependencies correspond to similar conclusions above-mentioned. In the case of the valve displacement of $s_2 = 2.31$ mm and the downstream pressure of $p_{3,rel.} = 0.5 \cdot 10^5$ Pa, a saturation can be additionally observed for the most frequently occurring bubble diameters. This indicates an already significant influence of the high bubble concentration and the distorted evaluation of bubble sizes.

D. Volume and mass fractions

Subsequently, the volume and mass fractions of released bubbles are evaluated with respect to the determined bubble size distributions and the recorded volume V_S . The assumption of a homogeneously dispersed gas phase can be introduced in the evaluation of the volume and mass fractions considering the vertical orientation of the observation window OW. At the same time, the spherical shape assumption of analyzed bubbles is introduced in the evaluation. The volume fraction of a single bubble is determined based on the bubble size which enters the volume of the recorded area V_S :

$$\alpha_{B,i} = \frac{1}{6} \pi d_{B,i}^3 \frac{1}{V_S}, \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_B = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{B,i}, \quad (8)$$

where $d_{B,i}$ is the i th bubble diameter. The volume fractions of analyzed bubbles are affected by the conditions at which the experiment is

FIG. 21. Selected statistical metrics based on lognormal distribution.

performed. The numbers and sizes of analyzed bubbles, including the volume fractions, are also affected by the compression of bubbles depending on the downstream pressure of the valve. To compare the obtained volume fraction dependencies under the different experimental conditions, these dependencies are determined for uniform pressure condition downstream of the valve (i.e., atmospheric pressure $p_{\text{ATM}} = 1 \cdot 10^5$ Pa):

$$\alpha_{B,\text{ATM}} = \alpha_B \frac{p_{3,\text{abs.}}}{p_{\text{ATM}}}. \quad (9)$$

The gas phase mass fractions are also determined and some simplifying assumptions are introduced. The first assumption is a very small mass fraction of the gas phase within the total mass of the mixture. The second assumption is the consideration that the interior of analyzed bubbles is predominantly filled by air. Thus, there is a complete condensation of the oil vapor when the pressure reaches higher than the oil vapor pressure of $p_{v,O} \approx 20$ Pa, or their representation in the analyzed bubble is negligible. The mass fraction of a single bubble, when the ideal gas equation is introduced, can then be determined as:

$$f_{B,i} = \frac{m_{B,i}}{m_O + m_{B,i}} \approx \frac{m_{B,i}}{m_O}, \quad (10a)$$

$$f_{B,i} = \alpha_{B,i} \frac{\rho_{B,i}}{\rho_O} = \alpha_{B,i} \frac{M_B}{\rho_O R T_B} \left(p_{3,\text{abs.}} + \frac{4\sigma_O}{d_{B,i}} \right), \quad (10b)$$

$$f_B = \sum_{i=1}^n f_{B,i}, \quad (11)$$

where $p_{3,\text{abs.}}$ is the absolute pressure in the observation window, $M_B = 28.96 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ is the air molar mass, $R = 8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ is the universal gas constant, T_B is the air thermodynamic temperature which is considered to be the same as the oil temperature, $T_O = T_B = 313.15 \text{ K}$, σ_O is the surface tension at the oil/air interface. The influence of the surface tension represents a small fraction of the change in the bubble density $\rho_{B,i}$ in comparison to the influence of the surrounding liquid pressure. The surface tension effect is neglected in the determination of mass fractions. In this way, it is possible to determine the volume and mass fractions of the released gas phase due to cavitation, while the effect of the suppressed cavitation zone is preserved under the different pressure conditions.

With respect to three acquired recordings of bubble size distribution measurements, time-averaged values of the released air volume and mass fractions from the dissolved state due to cavitation are determined. Fractions do not vary significantly over the recording time with the defined experimental conditions and can be considered almost constant over the recording time interval:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{B,\text{ATM}} = \frac{\alpha_{B,\text{ATM1}} + \alpha_{B,\text{ATM2}} + \alpha_{B,\text{ATM3}}}{3}, \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{f}_B = \frac{f_{B1} + f_{B2} + f_{B3}}{3}, \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha_{B,\text{ATM1}}$, $\alpha_{B,\text{ATM2}}$, $\alpha_{B,\text{ATM3}}$, f_{B1} , f_{B2} , f_{B3} are the resulting volume and mass fractions corresponding to a specific recording under identical experimental conditions. The air mass flow rates can be determined due to the almost consistent amount of air over the recording time interval:

$$Q_{m,B,\text{actual.}} = \bar{f}_B Q_{m,M} \approx \bar{f}_B Q_{m,O}, \quad (14a)$$

$$Q_{m,B,\text{actual.}} = \bar{\alpha}_{B,\text{ATM}} \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_O} Q_{v,O} = \bar{\alpha}_{B,\text{ATM}} \frac{p_{\text{ATM}} M_B}{R T_B} Q_{v,O}, \quad (14b)$$

where $Q_{m,M}$ is the mixture mass flow rate for which the assumption is introduced $Q_{m,M} \approx Q_{m,O}$, \bar{f}_B , and $\bar{\alpha}_{B,\text{ATM}}$ is the average mass and volume fraction of the gas phase within the 3×83 s recording time. The maximum air mass flow rate $Q_{m,B,\text{max.}}$, which can be potentially observed due to the release of air from the dissolved state, can be determined with respect to the known oil volume or mass flow rate $Q_{m,O}$ through the throttle edge of the valve:

$$Q_{m,B,\text{max.}} = f_{B,\text{DISS.}} Q_{m,M} \approx f_{B,\text{DISS.}} Q_{m,O}, \quad (15a)$$

$$Q_{m,B,\text{max.}} = \alpha_{B,\text{DISS.}} \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_O} Q_{v,O} = \alpha_{B,\text{DISS.}} \frac{p_{\text{ATM}} M_B}{R T_B} Q_{v,O}, \quad (15b)$$

where $f_{B,\text{DISS.}}$ and $\alpha_{B,\text{DISS.}}$ are the assumed mass and volume fraction of air that is in the dissolved state at atmospheric pressure p_{ATM} and mineral oil temperature $T_O = 40^\circ \text{C}$. The value of $\alpha_{B,\text{DISS.}} = 12\%$ is assumed in the calculation due to the higher air solubility in mineral oil at a higher temperature. The determined values of the maximum air mass flow rate $Q_{m,B,\text{max.}}$, which could be potentially released as bubbles, and the air mass flow rate $Q_{m,B,\text{actual.}}$ can be used to determine the percentage of released air from the dissolved state:

$$\zeta = \frac{Q_{m,B,\text{actual.}}}{Q_{m,B,\text{max.}}} 100 = \frac{\bar{f}_B}{f_{B,\text{DISS.}}} 100 = \frac{\bar{\alpha}_{B,\text{ATM}}}{\alpha_{B,\text{DISS.}}} 100. \quad (16)$$

The amount of released air from the dissolved state is related to the actual amount of mineral oil that passes through the throttle edge of the valve. The mineral oil can be considered as the carrier of the dissolved gas. The amount of dissolved gas, which can be potentially released in the form of bubbles when certain conditions are reached in the flow field, also increases as the oil mass flow rate increases. The amount of released air depends on achieved hydrodynamic flow parameters which can be uniformly characterized by the cavitation number.

Figures 22 and 23 show the resulting volume and mass fractions depending on the cavitation number for the different valve displacements of $s_1 = 1.31$ mm and $s_2 = 2.31$ mm whose cavitation zones are affected by different experimental conditions. Dependencies in Figs. 22 and 23 are shown in a logarithmic scale to provide better clarity in the region of small volume and mass fractions. Depending on the decreasing cavitation number, there is an increase in the amount of released gas phase which from a certain operating point follows a power law with a corresponding order of scaling. Figures 22 and 23 also indicate the extrapolated development of the gaseous phase due to cavitation which follows the defined approximation functions.

The determined trends represent the curves where the constant downstream pressure is reached and the flow velocity is increased in the narrowest flow area of the valve. Operating points, which are in the initial phase of cavitation occurrence or are affected by a high concentration of bubbles in the image, are not considered in the determination of approximation functions. The measured operating points in the initial phase of cavitation represent a deviation from the determined curve. Thus, the difference in the initial phase of cavitation suggests another physical process affecting the development of the gas phase. It may be the above-mentioned effect of turbulence at the valve or the phase change effect when the oil vapor pressure is reached. It can be assumed that the initial phase of the multiphase flow development in relation to cavitation is rather influenced by gaseous cavitation where there is a local reduction of the static pressure below the saturation pressure of the dissolved gas and the release of bubbles with increasing flow velocity. As the mean flow velocity continues to increase at a constant downstream pressure, a local static pressure is further reduced and conditions for the occurrence and development of vapor cavitation could be achieved. It can be said from the obtained operating points in the initial phase of cavitation that a more noticeable effect is achieved in the case of higher downstream pressures of

FIG. 22. Dependencies of time-averaged volume fraction on cavitation number.

FIG. 23. Dependencies of time-averaged mass fraction on cavitation number.

the valve. As the downstream pressure $p_{3,rel}$ decreases, less deviation from the determined curves is achieved and effects relating to the change of the development are not so significant. Different curves of volume and mass fractions can be observed for the different valve displacements in Figs. 22 and 23. In the case of larger valve opening $s_2 = 2.31$ mm, a more progressive increase in the gas phase (follows almost uniform scaling $\alpha_{B,ATM} \sim \sigma_{v2}^{-3.925}$) with decreasing cavitation number can be observed from a certain operating point, when vapor cavitation is reached. The steepness of determined curves is influenced by the size of nucleation sites where conditions for the cavitation occurrence and development are achieved due to a high flow velocity. Conversely, in the case of smaller valve opening $s_1 = 1.31$ mm, a deceleration of the gas phase growth (follows almost uniform scaling $\alpha_{B,ATM} \sim \sigma_{v2}^{-2.321}$) with decreasing cavitation number can be observed from a certain operating point, when vapor cavitation is reached. The effect of increasing downstream pressure on the reduced concentration of analyzed bubbles in the recorded area V_S is noticeable for both valve displacements. This is subsequently manifested in lower volume and mass fractions of the released gas phase at nearly identical cavitation numbers.

The approximation function of the volume and mass fraction development due to cavitation can be generalized as follows:

$$y = Ax^n, \tag{17}$$

where A is the power law coefficient, x is the variable, and n is the order of power law scaling. The power law parameters vary due to changing experimental conditions and valve displacements. For the sake of illustration, synthetic data are shown in Fig. 24 to characterize the effect of power law parameters on the resulting gas phase

FIG. 24. Influence of power law parameters on resulting development of gaseous phase – (a) standard scale and (b) logarithmic scale.

FIG. 25. Percentage of released gaseous phase from dissolved state.

development. The resulting curves are shown in the standard Fig. 24(a) and logarithmic scale Fig. 24(b).

The following findings can be found with respect to the empirically determined development of the gas phase due to cavitation. The increasing downstream pressure of the valve significantly affects the power law coefficient A in comparison to the power law exponent n . As the downstream pressure increases, the coefficient A decreases for both valve displacements. Consequently, the lower value of the power law coefficient A results in a suppressed development of the gas phase as the cavitation number decreases. The change of the power law exponent n is not so explicit and significant with increasing downstream pressure. However, this parameter becomes more noticeable with a change of the valve displacement. As the valve opening increases, the power law exponent n increases and the development of the gas phase becomes more progressive as the cavitation number decreases. A small change in the cavitation number subsequently leads to a proportionally large change in the amount of released gas phase. This conclusion can be observed in Figs. 22 and 23 where the power law exponent n affects the steepness of determined curves. The percentage of the gas phase, which is released from the dissolved state due to cavitation, can be observed in Fig. 25. There is an assumption that $\alpha_{B,DISS} = 12\%$ of air is initially dissolved in the mineral oil at the atmospheric pressure and oil temperature $T_O = 313.15\text{ K}$.

Different rates of mineral oil outgassing are achieved due to the different experimental conditions and the valve displacements. At the same time, it can be assumed from the extrapolated gas phase development that complete outgassing would occur at higher cavitation numbers in the case of larger valve opening of $s_2 = 2.31\text{ mm}$.

IV. CONCLUSION

The experimental study deals with the occurrence and development of cavitation in the throttle valve at the initial phase during the mineral oil flow HV46 when relatively low operating pressures are reached. The effect of flow velocity, downstream pressure and valve displacement on the development of the gas phase due to cavitation is evaluated. The following findings can be formulated with respect to the results obtained from the experimental study:

1. The occurrence of cavitation in the throttle valve does not significantly affect the static characteristics of the mineral oil flow under the defined experimental conditions. This is caused by the small cavitation zone which does not affect flow through the throttle valve and does not cause a choked flow condition. Also, gas release process is not connected only to the choked flow condition.

2. The visible occurrence of cavitation and intense release of the gas phase occurs at the point where the liquid jet is detached from the throttle valve body. This is caused by the angle of the liquid jet detachment where a high flow velocity causes a local static pressure decrease and a liquid tensile load over a larger region.
3. In the case of larger valve opening, the cavitation inception occurs at higher values of the cavitation number which indicates easier development of cavitation. It is assumed that a larger nucleation site in the flow field because of the valve displacement change is the cause of this condition.
4. The bubble size distributions are approximated by the lognormal distributions and the parameters of probability density function are evaluated. In essence, the parameters of lognormal distribution increase with decreasing cavitation number (i.e., increasing cavitation intensity).
5. The determined trends of the gas phase development due to cavitation are influenced by the change in the initial phase of occurrence. It can be assumed that the different physical process, i.e., gaseous cavitation, is the reason for the observed condition which is responsible for the bubble release in the initial phase of occurrence.
6. The dependence of air volume and mass fractions on the cavitation number can be suitably described by the power law with the appropriate order of scaling. The gas phase development follows almost uniform scaling when the vapor cavitation is reached. The increasing downstream pressure significantly affects the power law coefficient. The change of the power law exponent is not so explicit and significant with increasing downstream pressure. However, this parameter becomes more noticeable with the change of the valve displacement.
7. Depending on the experimental conditions and valve displacements, up to 1 vol. % of air is observed in the observation window. At the same time, it is assumed that up to 8% of air is released from the dissolved state.

Also, the cavitation phenomenon on the valve can be quantified by the released bubbles using the optical method. These data can then be used to optimize the valve geometry to reduce the intensity of cavitation. With respect to the determined bubble sizes, further experimental studies will be performed using a macro lens with a higher maximum magnification ratio, eventually again in combination with extension tubes, to achieve better resolution of bubbles. However, a significant reduction in the depth of field of acquired images will have to be taken into account. For this reason, an appropriate modification of the flow area of the observation window should also be considered. In the performed experiment, a small number of valve openings are achieved at which measurements are realized under the defined conditions. It is recommended to modify the transparent block to achieve more valve positions and a higher pressure load capacity of the block.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Tomáš Polásek: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Adam Bureček:** Conceptualization (equal); Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Lumír Hružík:** Funding acquisition (lead); Project administration (lead); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Marian Ledvoň:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal). **Filip Dýřr:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Róbert Olšiak:** Writing – review & editing (equal). **David Kolár:** Investigation (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in [Zenodo] at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13300822> (Ref. 43).

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